

A CAE-based Tool for Energy-Optimal Trajectory Planning in Automatic Machines

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Abstract—Position-controlled Servo-Mechanisms, commonly referred to as *electronic cams*, are widely employed in automatic machines in order to increase flexibility and versatility. Nonetheless, at the state-of-the-art, these mechatronic devices are still sub-optimized when energy consumption is considered as a performance metric. In fact, the industrial scenario is missing not only energy-efficient hardware (available though cost ineffective), but also virtual prototyping platforms allowing to effectively compute energy-optimized motions. In this context, the purpose of the present abstract, is to introduce a CAE-based tool, conceived with non-experts in mind, that allows to determine energy-optimal point-to-point trajectories, starting from a virtual model of the servo-system, built in a Computer-Aided-Engineering environment.

Index Terms—Servo-Mechanisms, Virtual Prototyping, Trajectory comparison, Eco-Design Methods, CAD/CAE tools.

I. INTRODUCTION

Energy efficiency in automatic machines is becoming a topic of primary importance due to forthcoming policy directives and increasing energy costs in several countries [1]. Considering that 45% of the global electricity consumption is due to the usage of electric motors [2], any potential energy-saving strategy may lead to remarkable improvements. For instance, in the field of automatic machines, mono-actuator systems (comprising a single motor coupled to cams or linkages) are progressively being substituted with multi-actuator architectures, where each task is accomplished by a dedicated mechanism driven by a position-controlled electric motor. An interesting industrial example is provided in Fig. 1, which depicts the CAD models and the physical prototypes of an automatic machines for the production of brushes, produced by *Borghi S.p.a.* (www.borghi.com). In its first design, a mono-actuator architecture is employed, resulting in a *rigid* system with no possibilities of adjustment. In its latter design, mechanical cams have been replaced by a set of Servo-Mechanisms (SMs), thus allowing a fast and effective change of the product format. Naturally, an increased number of SMs leads to an increased use of electric energy. Within this context, energy optimization methods are needed, which may be conceptually divided in two macro-areas:

- *Eco-design methods*, Energy Consumption (EC) reduction being reached by introducing new efficient hardware [3].

- *Eco-programming methods*, where EC is minimized by optimizing the production scheduling and the SM programming [4].

As for the latest case, portions of the SM end-effector motion law may be designed so as to drastically reduce the system EC. For instance, algorithms for the generation of energy-optimal Point-To-Point (PTP) motions have been proposed in e.g. [5], whereas a comprehensive reference of trajectory planning methods can be found in [6]. Following a similar direction, the aim of the present abstract is to briefly introduce a Computer-Aided-Engineering (CAE) tool conceived to help plant designers in optimizing PTP motions. Starting from a CAE representation of the mechanical system and a simple lumped-parameter model of the drive components, the user can automatically compute a PTP trajectory aimed at minimizing either SM torque or EC, thus allowing to save energy while avoiding any hardware substitution.

II. DESCRIPTION OF THE CAE TOOL

Having non-experts in mind, the motion design tool proposed in this abstract, whose conceptual schematic is depicted in Fig. 2, is characterized by the following features:

- A general purpose CAD/CAE software comprising motion analysis capabilities (in this case, *SolidWorks*), is used for creating the dynamic model of the mechanical system. A look-up table, in the form of a *.txt* file, that contains data concerning the reduced moment of inertia is automatically exported via an *API*.
- a *Matlab* script, employing as input the above-mentioned table plus basic motor parameters (i.e. equivalent electric resistance, back emf constant, motor torque constant), is then run. As output, the script provides torque-optimal and energy-optimal PTP motions, starting from an initial trajectory described by a 5-th order polynomial function.

The trajectory optimizer, the knowledge of the coding being of no use for the end-user, is characterized as follows:

- A gradient-free pattern search algorithm is employed for offline optimization. Task constraints on a series of way-points are easily included, whereas portions of the SM motion which are process-relevant are left unaltered.
- Motion profiles are generated via cubic or quintic splines interpolating a series of uniformly distributed knots.

Fig. 1: Automatic machine for the production of brushes: cam-based (*Design a*) and SM-based (*Design b*) architectures. Red circle: single actuator. Blue circles: multiple electric motors.

Fig. 2: Tools integration and optimization loop.

- Optimization cost functions are based on either the motor RMS torque or a simplified model of the SM electric energy consumption.

III. EXEMPLARY RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

As an exemplary case study, a slider-crank mechanism driven by a *Beckhoff AM3032C* Brushless motor coupled to *Wittenstein SP060S-MF1-7* gear reducer is considered. Detailed system parameters can be found in [7]. The initial PTP trajectory, which is taken as the reference motion for comparison purposes, is a fifth-order polynomial, namely the uniquely defined RMS jerk-optimal PTP motion. The optimizer computes optimal trajectory allowing for a 25% reduction of RMS torque or a 19.5% EC reduction over a defined cycle time (i.e. 0.6s). Initial and optimal trajectories, along with torque and power curves are plotted in Fig. 3. Since the practical implementation of any PTP trajectory on programmable SM is easily archived, the mentioned tool

can represent an effective aid for designers of servo-driven automatic machines.

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Fig. 3: Example of results obtained by minimizing either motor torque or energy.